

Benzene- and Naphthalene-azo-*o*-coumaric Acids.

BY DUKKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI.

Borsche (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 346) observed that an alkaline solution of coumarin, like a phenol, forms an azo-compound when coupled with diazotised aniline. To obtain definite information about the question as to whether hydroxyazo-compounds are azophenols or quinone-phenylhydrazones, Mitchell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1229) and Hewitt and Mitchell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 13, 17) prepared a series of azo-compounds by coupling diazo-salts with coumarin in alkaline solution.* They failed to isolate benzeneazocoumaric acid due to the ready formation of the lactonic ring. While investigating the effect of the lactonic group on the colour of an azo-dye, it has been thought advisable for a comparative study to break up the lactones and isolate the free hydroxy acids, and accordingly the corresponding azo-*o*-coumaric acids, the geometrical isomers of the azo-coumarinic acids, have been prepared.

It is interesting to find that when an alkaline (about 1%) solution of the benzene- and naphthalene-azocoumarins is boiled for some time with a small quantity of mercuric oxide (red or yellow), the sodium salts of the azocoumarinic acids undergo geometrical inversion quantitatively to the salts of the azo-*o*-coumaric acids. In this respect the azo-grouping behaves like a negative substituent (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247). The action of mercuric oxide seems to be purely catalytic as it remains unchanged at the end of the operation.

That the acids, thus isolated, are not azo-coumarinic acids but azo-*o*-coumaric acids, is conclusively proved by the direct synthesis of some of them from *o*-coumaric acid itself. Thus benzene-azo-*o*-coumaric acid (Borsche and Streitberger, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4116), *p*-nitrobenzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid, diphenylbisazodi-*o*-coumaric acid, naphthalene- α -azo-*o*-coumaric acid have also been directly synthesised from *o*-coumaric acid by coupling it in an alkaline solution with diazotised aniline, *p*-nitraniline, benzidine and α -naphthylamine respectively.

* When the 6-position in the coumarin molecule is free, coupling takes place in the 6-position, as is proved by the reduction of benzeneazocoumarin to 6-amino-coumarin.

These azocoumaric acids are beautifully crystalline substances, readily soluble in alcohol and other solvents unlike the corresponding azocoumarins, which are very difficultly soluble in the ordinary solvents. They dissolve freely in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. The colour of these dyes varies from yellow to red and even the naphthalene-azocoumarins (α and β) are yellow to brown, while the corresponding naphthalene-azo-*o*-coumaric acids have a green tinge.

A remarkable phenomenon which has been observed in the case of all these azo-*o*-coumaric acids is that they undergo in the solid state a marked change of colour when in contact with hydrochloric acid, the colour changing on dilution of the acid. Thus in the presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid, the yellow diphenyl-bisazodi-*o*-coumaric acid becomes violet, the naphthalene- α -azo-*o*-coumaric acid (greenish-yellow) becomes deep green, the original colour of the compounds being recovered on dilution (*vide* Table I). This change of colour seems to give a direct experimental evidence to the hypothesis advanced by Hewitt and his collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 160; 1905, 87, 225) that the *p*-hydroxyazocompounds are true azophenols and not quinonephenylhydrazones and that in the presence of strong mineral acids they may possibly possess a quinonoid constitution in the form of salts.

It is noteworthy however, that the azo-derivatives of the 4-alkyl-coumarins do not generally form *o*-coumaric acids by this method probably due to the instability of the β -alkyl-*o*-coumaric acids (Fries and Klostermann, *Annalen*, 1908, 362, 1); only in the case of benzeneazo-4:6-dimethylcoumarin the corresponding *o*-coumaric acid has been isolated in very poor yield. This acid also seems to be very unstable readily changing back into the coumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

*Benzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid.*—A solution of benzeneazocoumarin (Mitchell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 1229) (3 g.) in caustic potash (4 g. in 25 c.c. water) is diluted with water (500 c.c.) and boiled for about an hour with powdered yellow mercuric oxide (3 g.). The

cold solution is filtered from the mercuric oxide and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The reddish-yellow precipitate, thus obtained, is thoroughly washed with water and dissolved in ammonia. The ammoniacal solution is filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine yellow needles, decomposing at 205°. (Found: N, 10·5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10·44 per cent.).

The identical benzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid decomposing at 205° has also been synthesised from *o*-coumaric acid by diazotising aniline (1·1 g.) and coupling it with an alkaline solution of *o*-coumaric acid (2 g.). The precipitate, obtained after acidifying the alkaline solution, is dissolved in ammonia and the filtered solution is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 10·53. $C_{15}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10·44 per cent.).

Reduction of Benzeneazocoumarin.—Benzeneazocoumarin is reduced with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. The solution is made alkaline with caustic soda and the voluminous precipitate is extracted with boiling water, when 6-aminocoumarin melting at 167° crystallises in beautiful straw-yellow needles.

o-Nitrobenzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid is prepared from *o*-nitrobenzeneazocoumarin (Mitchell, *loc. cit.*). The method of isolation and the purification of the compound is the same as in the previous case; crystallised from dilute alcohol, it decomposes at 223°. It is a brownish-yellow substance. (Found: N, 13·7. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13·4 per cent.).

m-Nitrobenzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid is obtained from *m*-nitrobenzeneazocoumarin (Mitchell, *loc. cit.*). The compound is isolated as usual. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol in microcrystalline deep yellow powder decomposing at 213°. (Found: N, 13·33. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13·4 per cent.).

p-Nitrobenzeneazo-*o*-coumaric acid prepared from *p*-nitrobenzeneazocoumarin (Mitchell, *loc. cit.*), is crystallised from dilute alcohol. It is a reddish-yellow substance decomposing at 236°. (Found: N, 13·62. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13·4 per cent.).

The identical compound has been prepared directly from *o*-coumaric acid by coupling diazotised *p*-nitraniline with an alkaline solution of *o*-coumaric acid. The precipitate, obtained after acidifying the alkaline solution is dissolved in ammonia and is reprecipitated with acid. The precipitate is washed with water and crystallised

from dilute alcohol; decomp. 236° . (Found: N, 13.28. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N_3$ requires N, 13.4 per cent.).

Diphenylbisazodicoumarin.—Tetrazotised benzidine solution is added to an alkaline solution of coumarin and the mixture kept overnight. The solution is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the voluminous precipitate is filtered and thoroughly washed with boiling water. The dried residue crystallises in beautiful needles (not melting up to 280°) from a large volume of boiling nitrobenzene. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with a red solution and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet solution. It is insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents. (Found: N, 11.56. $C_{30}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires N, 11.24 per cent.).

Diphenylbisazodi-o-coumaric acid is obtained from diphenylbisazodicoumarin as in the previous cases. The dried crude product is dissolved in pyridine and poured into toluene when a yellow precipitate is obtained which is filtered and washed with benzene. It is a micro-crystalline yellow substance decomposing at 315° . (Found: N, 10.66. $C_{30}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.5 per cent.).

The identical diphenylbisazodi-o-coumaric acid, decomposing at 315° , has also been obtained directly from o-coumaric acid by coupling tetrazotised benzidine solution with an alkaline solution of o-coumaric acid. It is finally dissolved in pyridine and poured into toluene and the yellow precipitate collected. (Found: N, 10.72. $C_{30}H_{22}O_6N_4$ requires N, 10.5 per cent.).

Naphthalene-a-azocoumarin.—It is prepared by adding diazotised α -naphthylamine solution to an alkaline solution of coumarin. The filtered solution is then acidified with hydrochloric acid and the red precipitate is filtered and thoroughly washed with boiling water. The precipitate is then crystallised from toluene in stout brown prisms or needles melting at 217° . It dissolves in caustic alkalis forming a deep-red solution and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a blue solution. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.3 per cent.).

Naphthalene-a-azo-o-coumaric acid is prepared from naphthalene-a-azocoumarin and is crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining greenish-yellow needles decomposing at $198-200^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 9.1. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent.).

The identical naphthalene-a-azo-o-coumaric acid decomposing at $198-200^{\circ}$ has also been obtained directly by coupling diazotised α -naphthylamine with an alkaline solution of o-coumaric acid. It

is finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining yellow needles. (Found: N, 9.05. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent.).

Naphthalene- β -azocoumarin is prepared by coupling diazotised β -naphthylamine with an alkaline solution of coumarin. The red solution, after keeping overnight, is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered and thoroughly washed with boiling water. The substance crystallises from pyridine in beautiful needles. It also crystallises from toluene, in which it is not so much soluble. It is a yellow substance melting at 271° ; it dissolves in caustic alkalis (an orange solution) and in concentrated sulphuric acid (a deep-red solution). (Found: N, 9. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.3 per cent.).

Naphthalene- β -azo-o-coumaric acid is prepared from naphthalene- β -azocoumarin. It crystallises from dilute alcohol as a micro-crystalline pale yellow substance, decomposing at 210° . (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 8.8 per cent.).

Benzeneazo- β :5-dimethyl-o-coumaric acid is prepared from benzeneazo-4:6-dimethylcoumarin. The procedure of dissolving in ammonia and precipitating with acetic acid is repeated several times, as the compound seems to be very unstable and forms a turbid solution in ammonia which is very difficult to filter. It is then dissolved in alcohol and poured into water and the solid, that separates, is collected and extracted with ether. It decomposes at 186° (yield 20%). (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.46 per cent.).

TABLE I.

Colour of Azo-o-coumaric Acids.

Name.	...	Colour in the solid state.	Colour with alkalis.	Colour with conc. sulphuric acid.	Colour with conc. hydrochloric acid.
Benzeneazo-o-coumaric acid	...	Yellow	Orange	Red	Red
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-o-coumaric acid	...	Brownish-yellow	Deep-red	Deep-red	Reddish-brown
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-o-coumaric acid	...	Deep-yellow	„	Red	Brick-red
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzeneazo-o-coumaric acid	...	Reddish-yellow	Scarlet-red	„	Reddish-brown
Diphenylbisazodi-o-coumaric acid	...	Yellow	Deep-red	Deep-violet	Violet
Naphthalene- α -azo-o-coumaric acid	...	Greenish-yellow	Port wine-red	Bluish-violet	Deep-green
Naphthalene- β -azo-o-coumaric acid	...	Pale-yellow	Light-red	Deep-violet	Red

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY.
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

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